

The Impact of the Russian-Ukrainian War on European Security

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Abstract

The article aims to analyse the existing approaches to determining the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war on European security and the scenarios of further involvement of Ukraine's partners from both sides of the Atlantic in its protection. The most tangible consequences of the war for the European security environment are highlighted. Specific attention is paid to the debatable issues, such as approaches to how Ukraine can win, factors that prevent larger military aid from the West to Kyiv, threats stemming from an incomplete understanding by some Western leaders of Moscow's goals in the war. The study is centred on a critical analysis of publications on this topic in authoritative journals on international relations, statistical data on the aid of the states of the collective West to Kyiv, and the results of public opinion polls on the continuation of support for Ukraine's struggle in European states and the United States.

Keywords

Russian-Ukrainian war; EU; NATO; European security; USA

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Introduction

More than two years have passed since the Russian invasion of Ukraine. But as early as November 2023, the then Ukrainian commander-in-chief, General Valeriy Zaluzhnyi, changed the direction of the discussion about the war in his interview for *The Economist*, where he noted that a powerful technological leap is needed to break the deadlock, otherwise “a deep and beautiful breakthrough, rather than everything will not be” (*The Economist* 2023). Although the President of Ukraine Volodymyr Zelenskyi later repeatedly emphasized that the war was “not at a stalemate” (*Fox News* 2023), from the end of autumn 2023 this narrative dominated (*Ashford & Grieco* 2024; *Biddle* 2024; *Fix & Kimmage* 2023a; *Haass & Kupchan* 2023). The momentum created by Ukraine’s success in the first year of the conflict has given way to a sense that despite the ongoing fighting, the front line is not moving and the risk of a protracted positional war is growing.

Ukrainian achievements in 2022 near Kyiv, Kharkiv, and Kherson fuelled hopes that new efforts, bolstered by Western equipment and training, would allow a counteroffensive to break through Russian defences on a larger scale and block the land bridge to Crimea. Many believed that a further threat to Crimea could convince Putin to end the war. The results, unfortunately, did not live up to such expectations. Although Ukraine made important progress in the second half of 2023, pushing the Russian Black Sea fleet further east (allowing Kyiv to resume grain exports, withdraw troops stationed along the coast, and send them to the front), optimism that it can quickly be achieved in military terms on land, faded.

What does this mean for the future of war, for Ukraine, and, more broadly, for European security? Reliable answers require data that are not yet publicly available, but it is generally understood that without a breakthrough in the offensive, success in land warfare becomes hostage to a struggle of attrition. A favourable outcome for Ukraine in such a war is not impossible, but it requires Ukraine and its Western partners to adapt to a difficult confrontation with a numerically superior enemy, which could be very long.

Against this background, some scientists and politicians have concluded that the only right thing for Ukraine is a turn to a defence strategy, focused on guaranteeing the security of the territories currently controlled by Kyiv, which will ensure further support from partners and may eventually bring a despairing Putin to the negotiating table (*Ashford & Grieco* 2024; *Haass & Kupchan* 2023). But such conclusions reflect a fundamental misunderstanding of Moscow’s goals, which go beyond the ground war and are aimed at destroying the Ukrainian state, ending support for Ukraine from the US and Europe, and weakening NATO (*Seely* 2023). As long as Russia is capable of waging war in Ukraine, it will continue to wage war. A necessary prerequisite for peace and European security is the military defeat of Russia (*Sherr* 2024). Any outcome that would leave Putin with a large part of Ukraine would allow him to claim that he has cornered NATO at Russia’s doorstep, declare victory, and rearm for new waves of direct or indirect conflict. Such a scenario would lay the groundwork for further war on the European continent and probably bring it closer to NATO territory. Western officials should recognize this fact and undertake to support Kyiv with renewed vigor.

Ukraine and Russia will continue to compete to restore offensive combat power, and the weapons and personnel each side accumulates over the coming months will determine the long-term trajectory of the conflict. Uncertainty about the extent of further US and European support for Ukraine risks giving Russia advantages on the battlefield and further emboldening Moscow, which believes it can outlast the will of the West. At the same time, the transition from a half-hearted to a clear strategy for the victory of Ukraine, which would provide Kyiv with all the necessary weapons to push back the Russian forces and liberate its territory, would be able to provide the necessary leverage for

negotiations in the future and to impose a lasting peace on the aggressor. Ukraine and the West desperately need a common vision of the victory of Ukraine, a corresponding strategy, and the provision of resources that would correspond to this strategy (Sherr 2024).

Aid to Ukraine is not charity. The Russian invasion and the subsequent courageous resistance of the Ukrainian people became a turning point for the transatlantic security system, demonstrating the value and importance of Ukraine to Europe. Ukraine's victory or defeat will determine the future security of the entire continent. For the United States, the outcome of the war will determine the fate of the international order it presides over. Therefore, Europe and the United States should do more to protect Ukraine by formulating a joint vision for the long-term security of Ukraine and Europe.

The purpose of the article is to analyse and systematize existing approaches to the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war on European security and scenarios for the further involvement of Ukraine's partners from both sides of the Atlantic in its protection. The article analyses the most significant consequences of the war for the European security environment. We pay special attention to issues that remain debatable, such as approaches to how Ukraine can win; factors that prevent larger and faster military aid from the West to Kyiv; threats stemming from an incomplete understanding by some Western leaders of Moscow's true goals; ways that the EU and NATO can support Ukraine not only on the battlefield, but also by integrating Ukraine into its institutions to guarantee its future security and restore stability and peace in Europe.

The study is based on a critical analysis of publications on this topic in authoritative professional publications on international relations, on the pages of which views of representatives of various scientific schools are constantly presented regarding the course of the Russian-Ukrainian war and possible ways to stop the escalation. Statistical data on the aid of the collective Western states to Ukraine of the Kiel Institute of World Economy and the results of public opinion polls in European states regarding the continuation of support for Ukraine's struggle by the European Council on International Relations were also considered. Chronologically, the analysis covers the two years of the war from February 24, 2022. The main limitation of the study is that the conflict is still ongoing, so its long-term consequences for Ukraine and European security are difficult to predict, and therefore predicting any scenarios in this situation is analytically difficult and may turn out to be futile.

Changes in the security environment in Europe under the influence of the war

It is difficult to predict how deep the consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war will be for the world and the global order. However, even today the conflict is noticeably changing the contours of the European and Euro-Atlantic security architecture. We agree with Angela Stent that the final result of the Russian-Ukrainian war could be the third reorganization of the Euro-Atlantic security system since the end of World War II. The first took place with the consolidation of the Yalta-Potsdam system into two warring blocs at the end of the 1940s – the middle of the 1950s of the 20th century. The second, in the late 1980s – early 1990s, with the collapse of the communist bloc and the Soviet Union, which was followed by the expansion of Western structures and, above all, NATO to the East. Now Putin is challenging this order with his actions (Stent 2022). Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 was a transformative moment for European security, and the consequences of Kyiv's victory or defeat will determine either its further consolidation and strengthening or the prospect of protracted conflicts that will ultimately shake and destroy its foundations.

When the Kremlin launched a full-scale war against Ukraine, it was convinced that the collective West was fragmented and lacked the strategic purpose to effectively counter its audacious goals and sinister methods (Sherr 2024). Putin's aggression was based on the idea that the US is losing

interest in its European allies, and that the latter are weak, divided, and dependent on Russian oil and gas (Zakaria 2024). These assumptions have been proven wrong. As Stephen Kotkin emphasizes, at the beginning of this war the West rediscovered its multifaceted power (Kotkin 2022). Critically important in this process was J. Biden's skilful diplomacy on the eve and in the first months of the invasion. He and his team used declassified intelligence to strengthen transatlantic relations and unite the wider democratic community, including Asian partners (Japan, South Korea, Taiwan), to impose massive economic sanctions against Russia, strengthen NATO's position in Europe, and provide aid for the defence of Ukraine (Sydoruk, Pavliuk & Shuliak 2023: 314-315). Today, the coalition that supports the Ukrainian military or imposes sanctions against Russia covers about 60% of world GDP and 65% of world military expenditures (Zakaria 2024).

During 2022 and the first half of 2023, the unity of the West exceeded all expectations, which resulted in the provision of military, economic, and humanitarian aid to Kyiv for more than 200 billion dollars during the two years of the war (Polyakova & Goldgeier 2024). But, unfortunately, it has not yet resulted in a clear vision of the victory of the Ukraine strategy. Instead of its formation and steadfast implementation, the United States became the epicentre of uncertainty about the West's goals in the conflict, being more concerned with not provoking further escalation than with stopping the ongoing escalation (Sherr 2024). Fear of escalation trumped long-term strategic vision. From 2022, President Biden has consistently seen NATO's greater involvement in supporting Ukraine as a path to World War III. Therefore, the USA resorted to detours to coordinate military assistance to Ukraine by the member states of the Alliance through the Rammstein format (Polyakova & Goldgeier 2024). US President Joseph Biden threw a lifeline for Ukraine, but he also created the conditions for a protracted war, which will be difficult for Kyiv to win.

The slow and gradual approach to providing military aid to Ukraine, and the delay in allocating new packages from the US since the end of 2023, gave Russia advantages on the battlefield and encouraged Moscow, which believed that it could survive the will of the West. In the period from August to October 2023, the volume of newly provided aid to Ukraine fell sharply, and the total value of new packages amounted to only 2.11 billion euros – this is the lowest amount since January 2022 (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024a). And while the West continues to argue over further aid to Kyiv, Russia is quietly strengthening its control over the territories it occupies in the south and east of Ukraine. When the frontline stabilized in 2023, the occupiers still held almost 18% of Ukrainian land, including about 25,000 square miles captured since February 2022 (Lewis 2024). What the USA and Europe will do during 2024 will determine whether they will finally get rid of the remaining illusions about Moscow and will more decisively participate in the protection of Ukraine and the foundations of European security. The prognosis for our country largely depends on the future help of the West, but even if it continues, the conflict will probably remain a positional war for a long time. Ukraine's success, therefore, will require it and its Western allies to endure a long and difficult war.

Today, Europe is experiencing the most devastating military conflict in generations. After Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, European support for Kyiv remained strong, bolstered by the willingness of EU governments to impose 13 rounds of sanctions against Russia (as of the end of February 2024). EU states and institutions provided Ukraine with a total of more than 144 billion euros in aid as of the end of winter 2024 (according to the Kiel Institute of the World Economy) – almost twice as much as the United States (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024b). In October 2022, the EU launched a training mission, within the framework of which about 40,000 Ukrainian military personnel were to be trained by the end of 2023 (24 countries are participating in it) (European External Action Service 2024). To help Ukrainian refugees, in the first months of the war, EU

governments activated the so-called Temporary Protection Directive, allowing Ukrainians to enter the EU and move freely between countries without going through the usual procedures.

On February 28, 2022, the Ukrainian government submitted an official application for EU membership, in June of the same year, EU heads of state decided to grant Ukraine the status of a candidate state, and at the December 2023 summit, the member states and Brussels gave the green light to start official negotiations on accession of Ukraine (and Moldova) to the EU. These decisions were a major change in the politics of a united Europe, hitherto unthinkable, but Putin's invasion made a positive response to the Ukrainian bid a strategic imperative. The future stability of Ukraine is now rightly seen as the key to the future stability of Europe. While the protection of the Ukrainian state will undoubtedly require stronger guarantees and security measures (preferably through NATO membership), most European leaders understand that Ukraine's political and economic integration into the EU is essential for future security in Europe, just like previous waves of enlargement helped ensure peace on the continent after the end of World War II.

As far as purely military aid is concerned, the EU countries continue to catch up, and in the second half of 2023, they surpassed the USA. In particular, Germany and the Nordic countries (Denmark, Norway, Sweden, and Finland) allocated significant new aid in the last months of 2023. Of the total 25 billion heavy weapons commitments (January 2022 – October 2023), the US accounts for 43% of the value, while all EU countries and institutions together account for 47% (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024a). The US remains the largest military donor, with total commitments of over €44 billion. But Germany is quickly catching up with them, Berlin's military aid currently exceeds 17 billion euros (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024b).

On February 1, 2024, 27 EU member states agreed on a four-year aid package for Ukraine worth 50 billion euros, which was blocked by Hungary in December 2023. This was an extremely important decision because, against the background of the Republicans blocking the allocation of American aid at the time, a further delay in the provision of EU support could lead to serious problems in Ukraine with the payment of salaries, pensions, and other critical expenses. With the final approval of this package, financial assistance to Kyiv for the coming years seems assured, but it is much less clear about military support.

The EU has so far been unable to significantly increase its ammunition production capacity due to a lack of planning and forecasting. It also failed to fulfil its commitment to provide Ukraine with one million artillery shells by March 2024, which it promised to provide within a year, in the spring of 2023. According to the statement of the EU High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, Josep Borrell, by March, the EU had fulfilled its promise by only 52%, and the rest will probably be provided by the end of the winter of 2024 (Government Portal 2024). As a result, out of 2.3 million projectiles used by Ukraine in 2023, only 300,000 were European (Gressel 2024). This lag has consequences on the battlefield. At the peak of the Ukrainian offensive, Russia used 25,000-30,000 shells per day, while Ukraine used only 7,000 (Röttgen 2023). By the end of 2023, Ukrainian forces were firing about 2,000 shells per day, while Russian artillery power, although reduced, was at the level of about 10,000 shells per day (Watling 2024). Faced with a critical shortage of ammunition, Ukrainian troops are forced to limit their use. If in the future Ukraine will not be able to create local conditions of artillery superiority, any new operations will lead to irreparable losses of Ukrainian troops.

Kyiv's Western allies squandered the temporary advantages they had in 2022-2023, enjoying the euphoria of Russia's first setbacks and hoping to avoid a protracted conflict. Instead of expanding industrial capacity in their countries, they mostly provided Ukraine with ammunition from national stocks or the international market. Now these stocks are running out.

According to Jack Watling, a senior research fellow in land warfare at the Royal Joint Services Institute, Kyiv would need about 2.4 million rounds of ammunition a year to achieve local artillery superiority. But it will be difficult for Ukraine's international partners, including the USA, to provide even half of this in 2024 (Watling 2024). The calculations of military expert Gustav Gressel from the European Council on International Relations and publicist and analyst Marcus Welsch also testify to the acute shortage of ammunition in Ukraine: Ukraine needs at least 5,000 standard shells per day or 1.8 million per year for "minimum protection" from Russia. Deliveries announced for 2024 from America and Europe are significantly lower than this figure – 3,600 shells per day or 1.3 million per year (Schuller 2024). The acute shortage of munitions jeopardizes the Ukrainian successes of the last two years. In this context, a lifeline for the Ukrainian armed forces can be the Czech initiative to purchase hundreds of thousands of projectiles for Ukraine at the expense of the European states that have volunteered to participate in it.

Part of the problem is that many European leaders, as well as the White House leader, have so far failed to clearly articulate the purpose of aid to Ukraine, instead pursuing a vague and often half-hearted strategy of support. Their gradual and slow approach to aid did not allow Kyiv to achieve a serious breakthrough during the summer offensive of the Armed Forces (the reasons for Ukraine's failure are well systematized and analysed in Biddle, 2024). Policymakers in the German government and some other European countries continue to view the delivery of each weapon system through the prism of how Russia will respond. Olaf Scholz's biggest flaw is that he remains vague when discussing the West's goals for supporting Ukraine. He continues to use an ambiguous formula: "Russia should not win, Ukraine should not lose" (Röttgen 2023). Instead, he should call the Russian war what it is: an attack on peace in Europe that poses security risks for Germany itself and the entire continent. Thus, recently French President Emmanuel Macron, to his great credit, recognized the importance of defeating Putin in Ukraine for the overall security of Europe. Such wording would probably contribute to maintaining a high level of approval of aid to Ukraine by the German and European public.

Polls conducted by the European Council on Foreign Relations (ECFR) show that European support for Ukraine's continued struggle has begun to decline. The change is still small, but its direction leaves no room for doubt. According to an older survey conducted in January 2023 in ten European countries (Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Switzerland), an average of 38% wanted Ukraine to regain its entire territory. But according to a subsequent survey conducted in September and October in the same states, that number dropped to 34% (Dennison & Zerka 2023). For comparison: September 2023 US data show that 43% support Ukraine as long as it continues to fight (Dennison & Zerka 2023).

The results of a survey conducted by the ECFR in January 2024 in 12 European countries (Austria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain and Sweden) show that Europeans are pessimistic about the outcome of the war. On average, only 10% of Europeans believe that Ukraine will win. Twice as many expect Russia to win. The answer of the overwhelming majority of respondents (37% on average) is that the war will end with a settlement, and by a margin the war outweighs the victory of Ukraine even in Poland (Krastev & Leonard 2024). Expecting a settlement does not mean giving preference to such an outcome, but it indicates pessimism about the possibility of the victory of Ukraine.

The same survey demonstrates a change in the geography of support for Ukraine. Previously, the generally accepted opinion was that Ukraine's closest neighbours are among its biggest supporters, both in terms of government support and in terms of the openness of societies to Ukrainian refugees. Currently, Ukraine seems to have the strongest public support in distant Portugal and France, while

solidarity with it is falling in some of its closest neighbours. Hungary, where the largest number of citizens expect a victory for Russia (31%), and where the majority of respondents would like to push Ukraine to a settlement (64%), is no longer an exception. Romania's indicators: 18% believe that Russia will win, and 50% want to push Ukraine to a settlement (see, also, Văscan and Iov, 2023). Most notably, however, in Poland, which has traditionally positioned itself as one of Ukraine's staunchest supporters, only 17% believe that Ukraine will win (Krastev & Leonard 2024). At the level of public opinion, ambiguous feelings towards Ukrainian refugees and the access of Ukrainian agricultural products to the Polish and European markets are also beginning to accumulate. The danger lies in the fact that when it comes to Ukraine's integration into the European Union, Ukraine's immediate neighbours may become among its fiercest opponents. Public support for Ukraine in Europe has not yet declined dramatically, but European leaders must do a better job of providing their voters with a compelling theory about how Ukraine can win the war and why it is important for the future of Europe.

The US and Europe are obligated to do more

The current situation on the battlefield is worrying for Ukraine and its partners. Enemy forces, bolstered by aid from China, Iran, and North Korea, took advantage of the almost six-month gap in US military support for Ukraine and accelerated their advance in some areas of the front. The possibility that they could break through Ukrainian defences along the eastern front and challenge Ukrainian control over Kharkiv or even Kyiv became a real threat. Russia has also increased its attacks on the civilian population and non-military infrastructure. At the beginning of April 2024, knowing that Ukraine lacked anti-aircraft ammunition, Russia launched a missile attack that destroyed the largest power plant in the Kyiv region. Earlier, in March, Russian troops attacked the dam of the hydroelectric power plant in Dnipro and other electrical facilities.

At the end of April 2024, a debate in the US Congress on the restoration of military aid to Ukraine ended with the approval of a major new package of more than 60 billion dollars, but the previous months of delays in Washington turned out to be tragic for Ukraine, spooked the Europeans, and gave Moscow hope that the determination of the West is cracking. Ukraine and Europe found themselves in a difficult strategic situation. But the war is not lost for Ukraine, and one should beware of defeat. A quick victory on the battlefield or negotiations in which Kyiv emerges from a strong position is unrealistic shortly. But given the role that external support and the limitations of that support have already played in the war, with adequate help from the West, the balance of advantages may once again turn against Russia. The Kremlin's prospects in a protracted war will critically depend on the scale and pace of Western support for Ukraine.

After both houses of Congress approved aid to Ukraine, it was time to change the strategy. What Ukraine and the transatlantic community need most is a shared vision of victory – the end state they want in clearly defined geostrategic terms – around which Kyiv and its supporters can rally. Instead of endlessly repeating that “we will support Ukraine as long as it takes,” we need to adopt the strategy “Ukraine must win”. Among the first actions should be the transfer of the necessary weapons to Ukraine, as well as the seized Russian assets. This approach carries a certain risk of escalation, but it alone gives Kyiv a chance to win.

The coalition of the richest and most technologically advanced countries gives Ukraine a great structural advantage. Russia has only two countries – Iran and North Korea – that openly help it in the war, although China remains an important economic support for it. The total defence budgets of the 54 countries that support Ukraine exceed \$100 billion per month. Instead, the current support of

Ukraine costs these states less than 6 billion dollars every month (Watling 2024). The biggest obstacles for Ukraine to win the war are political.

The main risk for Ukraine so far is not a sudden political change in the West, but rather the lack of a strategic vision of victory in Kyiv and, as a result, the slow unravelling of the carefully woven network of foreign aid. However, if a sudden change does happen, it will be linked to the US presidential election in November 2024. Therefore, political leaders in the US and Europe today must do everything possible to anchor financial and military aid to Ukraine in long-term budget cycles (as the EU has already done, approving in February 2024 more than 50 billion euros for Ukraine for 2024-2027), which will make it difficult for future officials to curtail support.

If US support and leadership are maintained, Ukraine will have a solid basis for hopes for its survival and a positive end to the long war. The loss of support from the US would have a dramatic effect. It will be difficult for Europe to replace US military aid on such a large scale, and it will be difficult to fill the leadership gap. If the US tried to force Ukraine into a negotiated settlement, the Europeans would have little opportunity to resist. But any short-sighted or hasty settlement would jeopardize both the security of Ukraine and the security of Europe and could demonstrate to Putin the diminishing commitment of the United States to guaranteeing the security of the European continent.

Some leaders in Western capitals, as well as analysts and researchers (for example, Richard Haas and Charles Kupchan (2023), Emma Ashford and Kelly A. Grieco (2024), now argue that Ukraine should focus only on defensive measures and embark on the path of search agreements on ending the war. However, this line of thinking does not take into account either the scale of Russia's goals or its unwillingness to negotiate in good faith. Putin, as before, wants to subjugate the whole of Ukraine, and not occupy part of its territory. In his opinion, Russia and Ukraine are one whole, and the existence of an independent Ukrainian nation is an anti-Russian conspiracy fabricated by foreign intervention (Gressel 2024). The Kremlin would be happy to negotiate the unconditional surrender of Kyiv, but today it has no obvious reason to make any concessions. The Russian economy can withstand the war, but there are still opportunities for additional mobilization. As it seems from the latest statements of the Kremlin dictator, he now imagines the "special military operation" as a multi-year war in which Russia will have enough resources to survive the will of the West and win. Negotiations now risk, at best, a repeat of the diplomacy of the Minsk agreements, which paved the way for a much more aggressive invasion eight years later (Fix & Kimmage 2023b). The idea that Ukraine can exchange land for peace and thus remain free in the territory it controls is a fantasy (Polyakova & Goldgeier 2024). A satisfactory agreement cannot be reached from Ukraine's positions of weakness, and there is no reason to believe that the defensive approach of Ukraine and its partners will encourage Russia to move towards a ceasefire. Financing a defensive war will never be enough to stop Putin. Ukrainian victory, on the contrary, can do it. But this result will require a radical change in strategic thinking in the White House and European capitals. Now Putin is betting on war fatigue in the West. The ideal scenario for him would be the second Trump administration, which would stop the support of Kyiv by the United States, and Europe's interest in the war would fade (Krastev & Leonard 2024).

However, European leaders cannot afford to let American political dysfunction dictate European security prospects. They must step up to ensure the protection of Europe, given the prospect of Donald Trump's return to the Oval Office (Röttgen 2023). This would correspond to the security interests of every European state. Europeans cannot change their geography. A great ocean does not separate them from the war. It was the collective peaceful European order that was attacked by Russia, so Europe had no choice but to support the Ukrainian victory. It would be much more difficult to support Ukraine alone (without the USA), but, according to German Bundestag member Norbert

Röttgen, it is not impossible. Germany's GDP alone is almost twice that of Russia's, and the EU as a whole is seven times larger than Russia's. We share his conviction that to activate the potential of the EU as a geopolitical player, Germany should live up to its leadership role in the bloc by supporting Ukraine. In 2023, German military aid to Ukraine already amounted to about 4 billion euros, including tanks and anti-missile defence systems, and this amount will be doubled in 2024 (Röttgen 2023). But to continue striking Russian infrastructure and supply lines, Ukraine needs cruise missiles like the Taurus, as well as fighter jets to ensure air superiority. The real reason for refusing to transfer this weapon to Kyiv is that it is extremely effective, and Olaf Scholz fears that its successful use could provoke an escalation on the part of Russia (Röttgen 2023). Although precious time has been lost, it is not too late for the German chancellor to act more decisively.

To quickly ensure the supply of more artillery shells to Ukraine, the EU can limit the supply of ammunition to third parties to be able to make a much larger share of the existing production available to Ukraine. Recently, the High Representative of the EU for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, Josep Borel, said that supplies of ammunition from the European Union to third parties currently make up about 40% of European capacities, so it should be stopped to have the opportunity to redirect them to Ukraine (Schuller 2024). Many politicians in the German Bundestag share this view. Thus, the head of the German-Ukrainian parliamentary group, Robin Wagener, demanded that Europe "act faithfully" because "it would be a scandal if Ukraine had to give up its land while warehouses elsewhere are being filled" (Schuller 2024).

For an uninterrupted supply of ammunition in the future, it is necessary to increase military production and expand the production capabilities of European countries. Kyiv's acquisition of medium- and long-range cruise missiles, F-16 fighter jets, additional air defence systems (Patriot and IRIS-T missiles), and the necessary number of artillery shells will allow effective pressure on Russian forces and gain an advantage on the battlefield. Ukrainian victory requires Europe to invest in its defence industrial capacity so that it can support Ukraine even if Washington stops. Putin expects to survive Ukraine's support from the West, and his bet must be wrong. According to experts at the Kiel Institute of World Economy, Europe will have to at least double its current military aid efforts to Ukraine if the United States stops further support (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024b). This is a challenge, but ultimately a matter of political will. EU countries are among the richest in the world, and so far, they have not spent even 1% of their GDP to support Ukraine (Kiel Institute for the World Economy 2024b).

In addition to expanding their production capacity, Ukraine's partners can do more to slow Russia's arms production, including through proper enforcement of EU sanctions in a way that prevents Russia from circumventing them through third parties, as well as introducing much tougher sanctions against Iran to cut off supplies which are used to manufacture drones (where Western components are detected) (Röttgen 2023). It is significant that in the spring of 2024, the European Union began to consider the potential possibility of introducing sanctions against more than a dozen companies in Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, China, Hong Kong, and some other countries that continue to supply banned European goods to Russia.

In February 2024, French President Emmanuel Macron broke the taboo on discussing another way in which Europe could support Ukraine: the deployment of European troops here, saying that it cannot be ruled out. Although his idea caused predictable indignation not only in the Kremlin but also the objection of Washington and Berlin, the very appearance of such a discussion, as well as the support of the corresponding idea by high-ranking officials of Finland, Poland, and the Baltic States, is a serious breakthrough in the approaches of European countries to possible options for countering

Russian aggression. Sending European troops to Ukraine would be a normal response to a conflict of this kind. Even non-combat missions to provide logistical support and training and protect Ukrainian borders and critical infrastructure far from the front line west of the Dnipro could free up more Ukrainian forces for combat missions, reduce the likelihood of opening new fronts, and raise Ukrainian morale. France could take the lead in this initiative.

Ukraine's victory will not be determined only on the battlefield. Strategically, Western countries should intensify their efforts to integrate Kyiv into their institutions. Perhaps the most significant non-military support that Europe can offer Ukraine is a direct path to EU membership, as it is the only way to secure its future as a self-sufficient European, democratic country, with all the financial and security benefits that EU membership entails. The decision of the European Council in December 2023 to start pre-accession negotiations with Ukraine and Moldova was important in this regard (it is already a big victory for Europe and Ukraine), but it is only the first step on the long path of integration into the club, given the demands for reforms in Ukraine and the need for difficult decisions in the EU itself. Politicians should work to deepen ties between Ukraine and a united Europe, even if full EU membership is likely unrealistic for Kyiv until the end of the war.

Another key to counteracting Moscow's strategy of exhaustion and destruction and restoring a solid basis of regional security in Europe is decisive concrete action in the direction of Ukraine's future accession to NATO. Kyiv's membership in the Alliance is the only long-term means of deterring future Russian attacks. As long as it is fighting, Ukraine will not join NATO – that is clear. But already now, to prevent Russia from constantly threatening Kyiv in the long term, the Alliance should seriously consider the scenario of how and when it will be able to accept Ukraine so that the issue of Ukrainian membership moves forward. If, as a result of the fighting, Russia retains control over part of the Ukrainian territory (an extremely undesirable outcome for Ukraine and the West, which they will try their best to prevent and will never recognize the captured regions as part of the Russian Federation), the territory under the control of the Ukrainian government must be protected from future threats through membership in to prevent Russia and further inflame instability in Europe.

An official invitation to NATO is unlikely during this year's summit of the organization in Washington. But this meeting could give a start to the definition of a clear plan and conditions for the acceptance of the Ukrainian state into the Alliance (Polyakova & Goldgeier, 2024). In the future, much will depend on the success of Ukrainian defence operations, the liberation of its territory, and further reforms of the defence sector. Ukraine already has the most capable, battle-hardened army in Europe, which will become an asset, not a liability, to the Alliance. Decisive concrete actions by NATO at the July 2024 summit are needed, which will demonstrate that Ukraine's future is in the Alliance. It is also an opportunity for Joseph Biden to record the successes of his policy towards Kyiv before the US presidential elections at the end of 2024.

Conclusion

Since the front line is currently in a territorial stalemate, Ukraine's chances of regaining full control over the occupied territories by force of arms in 2024 look slim. But an exclusively defensive strategy focused on further dialogue with Russia would be fundamentally wrong and catastrophically naive. Simply funding a defensive war in Ukraine without changing the dynamics is likely to lead to Putin's victory over time. Any ceasefire or freezing of the conflict would draw a line through southern and eastern Ukraine, leave millions of Ukrainians under Russian rule, and result in a divided state with no hope of joining NATO or the EU. Putin could recover, regroup, and attack, and destabilize Ukraine again by any means available.

The West now faces a crucial choice that requires a change in strategic thinking: support Ukraine so that it can defend its territory and rebuild its forces for offensive operations, recapture the captured lands and exhaust the aggressor to the point of imposing a lasting peace, or give in to Russia, which believes that it can survive the will of the West. The first result is desirable, not only for Ukrainians. For Europe, success or failure in Ukraine's struggle will determine the security of the entire continent, and for the United States, the future of the world order, which they lead.

Developing and following a consistent and realistic victory for Ukraine strategy will require greater and faster military aid to the US and the EU, Europe investing in its defence industrial potential, strengthening sanctions against Russia and better ensuring their implementation, sending European troops to Ukraine, and opening a real path for Ukraine to join NATO and the EU. This will benefit all Europeans by restoring and expanding the area of peace, prosperity, and stability on the continent.

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